

Factors Influencing Consumer Purchase Intention: A Study of Bookstores in Kurdistan Region of Iraq

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ABSTRACT

Background problems: Due to the weakness of the banking system infrastructure, there is no online bookstore or E-commerce business in Kurdistan. Many customers complain about the problem of the parking facility, most of the bookstore locations have not enough parking space nearby for the customers to be able to visit the bookstores and spend quite enough time to search for books and buying them. **Main objective:** So, the researcher has decided to study the impact of social media marketing on customer purchase intention toward bookstores in Kurdistan region. **Research methods:** The sample of the study consists of 300 respondents of which 231 are males, and 69 are females. The instrument of the study is adapted from previously established studies. The first part of the survey was designed to investigate respondents' demographics, whereas, the second part focused on the independent and dependent variables of the study. **Finding:** The results showed that all the independent variables significantly influenced customer purchase intention toward bookstores in Kurdistan. **Contribution:** The findings of the study implied valuable contribution in two aspects. Theoretically, the study findings showed evidence for the establishment of TAM. In terms of managerial implication, the study provided a practical recommendation for the practitioners. The research findings come to validate SMM as a potential promotional strategy for bookstores in the region. **Conclusion:** So, bookstore marketers need to include social media marketing to their promotional strategy and improve social media marketing skills which can give advantage for the bookstores.

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INTRODUCTION

In the past, the traditional media was used by marketers such as newspaper, magazine, television, and radio and so on to promote the products. The traditional media was unable to customize the message to specific customers and the cost of ads in the old media was too much. So, the marketers were looking to an efficient media to communicate with the audience. Consequently, with the development of advanced technology and the internet, marketers have found social media as an effective and efficient tool to reach customers (Fridolf & Arnautovic, 2013). It is important to mention that the internet is different from social media, social media is a virtual platform that connects everybody around the world and where people can share information. However, social media cannot function or perform without the internet, and social media is a part of the internet.

Therefore, Yankova and Ozuem (2014) stated that it became a trend among marketers to use social media to communicate with their clients. Going back to the modern history of social media, the first invention that introduces social media to the market was a blog in 1991. After that, some other social media platforms were created such as LinkedIn and Myspace in the year 2000. Then the social media booms with the emergence of YouTube in 2005. Facebook and Twitter come out in 2006 and they are widely used around the world until today. Next, the American social media platform for sharing video and photo was launched in 2010. Finally, the latest social media platforms are the American messaging app known as Snapchat in 2011, followed by China's video-sharing platform Tik-Tok in 2016. So, all of them are still common and used until today 2020 (Gao, Tang, & Liu, 2012; Appel et al., 2020; Boon-

Long & Wongsurawat, 2015; Edosomwan, et al., 2011).

Furthermore, nowadays there are thousands of social media sites and it is expected that more advanced social media platforms will be available in the next decades. The number of people who are using the internet is almost 4.5 billion and there are approximately 3.8 billion active users of social media in 2020 (Kemp, 2020). As a result, the number of using traditional media has been dramatically reduced among companies (Othman, 2020).

It is observed by Ridley (2020) that social media is also a convenient platform for those who are interested in reading and buying books where they can discuss share opinion and comment on any books and bookstores which will affect the bookstore's brand either positively and negatively. Besides, social media is helpful for publishers to reach customers who like to read books and individualized the message to them. On the other hand, it has made the work easier for readers where they can conveniently get brief information wherever they are about the books and request the bookstore to have them instead of going to the bookstore and search physically for the books (Yang, 2009). Not only that, the social media can provide an instant insight on the customer's behaviour and intention which is useful for marketers to analyze the data and make a better marketing campaign (Fridolf & Arnautovic, 2013).

The ministry of culture in KRG (Kurdistan regional government) reported that there are almost 50 bookstores in the whole Kurdistan and 3000 new book titles are printed every year. Besides, the number of readers is approximately 122,000 out of 5.000.0000 population and the number of authors is estimated to be 150 (Bazgr, 2019).

According to (DATAREPORTAL, 2020), the number of people who are using the internet is

approximately 29 million in Iraq, and among this number 21 million of them are using social media in 2020. In the study of (Khorsheed & Othman,

2020) the participants were asked "do you use social media", so, all of them stated that they use social media 100%.

Table 1. The number of hours that people spend on social media per day in Kurdistan region of Iraq.

The number of hours per day	The percentage of people
1 to 3 hours	54.7%
Less than 1 hour	23.4%
4 to 7 hours	15.6%
More than 7 hours	6.3%

Source : (Khorsheed & Othman, 2020)

Table 1. shows the number of hours that people spend on social media per day in Kurdistan region of Iraq in the study of (Khorsheed & Othman, 2020). It can be extracted from the statistical data and the study above that, the high number of people in the Kurdistan region are using social media and they spend so much time on it per day. Which can be a great opportunity for the bookstores in the region to reach the customers through social media platforms and promote the books to them.

Among the social media platforms, Facebook has the highest number of users which is 55.04% in the whole of Iraq (DATAREPORTAL, 2020). Meanwhile, in a study by (Khorsheed & Othman, 2020) the participants were asked which social media site use the most, 78.1% of them stated that they are using Facebook. So, according to these statistics, it can be said that Facebook is the most popular platform in Iraq in general and Kurdistan region specifically. Therefore, Facebook can be considered as the most

effective platform to reach customers in the region. Hence, due to the lack of research on the impact of social media marketing on the bookstores, this research will be a starting point to see more study on the bookstores and it can be said that bookstore is one of the major business for any society that dreams to develop (Hovinga, 2019).

The objective of this study is by answering the following study:

1. What is the impact of social media marketing on customer purchase intention in the bookstores in Kurdistan?
2. What is the impact of perceived usefulness on customer purchase intention in the bookstores in Kurdistan?
3. What is the impact of perceived ease to use on customer purchase intention in the bookstores in Kurdistan?
4. What is the impact of attitude on customer purchase intention in the bookstores in Kurdistan?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theory of the Technology Acceptance Model

Figure 1. Technology acceptance model (Davis et al., 1989)

Figure 1. indicated the theory of technology acceptance model by (Davis et al., 1989) which is the impact of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use on behavioural intention to use with a moderate variable which is the attitude toward use. Also according to Oliveira and Martins, (2010), TAM is the most common model that has been implemented among the researchers on different studies relevant to the information system. TAM can be defined as the most considerable theory to discover how much the user accepts to use a specific information system and underlying the factors of accepting to utilize that technology. (Rauniar, et al., 2014). Chuttur (2009) stated that the goal of TAM model helps the academicians and industry experts to understand why a specific factor can be acceptable by the users and why not, along with the prediction about it.

It is noticed that the theory of Technology acceptance model is derived from the theory of reasoned action (TRA) which is used to study the customer's acceptable behaviour according to (Chuttur, 2009). Furthermore, to understand the development of TAM. TAM was first used by Fred Davis in 1986 in his doctorate proposal to examine users' acceptance of IS or technologies. Next, in 1989 Davis implemented TAM to investigate the behaviour of accepting computers through general determinants. Finally, the last version of TAM was done by Venkatesh and Davis in 1996 and the result of that study was that the PU and PEOU have a positive impact on user intention (Momani & Jamous, 2017).

Although the TAM theory has recorded great success and it is considered as a reliable model but, the form of TAM has been changed by including many variables into it (Mathieson, 1991). So, In the study of acceptable behaviour toward information technology and IS, several

theories have been formed by the scholars, which are the theory Reasoned action (TRA), then the Theory of planned behaviour (TPB) next, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM, TAM2) and finally Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) based on (Lai, 2017). Moreover, there was a study to compare the Technology acceptance model with the theory of planned behaviour to use telemedicine technology and the result was that the TAM is greater to TPB in examining the intention of physicians (San & Yee, 2013).

Customer purchase intention

Purchase intention can be defined as the tendency of individuals toward buying a product or taking any action (Kim & Chung, 2011). It is also defined by Perdana et al. (2018) as a state of happiness that leads customers to spend money, time, and effort to purchase a product. Also, purchase intention interpreted as a motivation that encourages customers to take an action toward buying their desired product and service according to (Said et al., 2014). Apart from that, Awan et al. (2015) defined the purchase intention as a state where the customers prefer to buy the product, or it can be described that the customer intends to buy the product after the evaluation process. So, it can be extracted from the definitions that purchase intention is a state in which the customer already decided to buy a product but has not taken any action yet.

Along with that Turney and Littman (2003) also considered purchase intention as a significant cause that leads customers to take action and buy the product. So, purchase intention is a great indication of customer purchase behaviour. In other words, the purchase intention enables us to predict customer buying behaviour (Zeithaml, 2000). To put it simply, according to Majid, Sabir, and Ashraf (2020) purchase intention is "what you think you will buy". Customers with strong

positive intention tend to engage with the company or product which will end up with repurchase or being loyal to the brand (Mohezar, Zailani & Zainuddin, 2016). And also Keller (2001) mentioned that many factors affect the customer intention to make an ultimate decision on buying a particular product. Therefore, the purchase intention had a great impact on the company's sales because the process of customer buying decisions can be influenced by the intent of the customer (Haro, 2016). Finally, Valarie (1988) stated that purchase intention can be measured as "consideration to buy, the possibility to buy or willingness to buy. According to the (Nielsen, 2010), the purchase intention of customers has changed, and they prefer to buy and search for books in the virtual environment rather than visiting the physical bookstore. The study of Nguyen et al. (2020) showed that virtual communication is one factor that influences customer purchase intention to buy books from the bookstores.

Social media marketing and customer purchase intention

Social media marketing is a part of internet marketing and it is all about how to use social media platforms to market the products (Motameni & Nordstrom, 2014). Meanwhile, Miller (2013) stated that social media marketing is a powerful tool that can be used for every type of business to engage with current and reach potential customers. Therefore, social media marketing can be used in the bookstores as well and can be defined in the concept of the bookstore as utilizing social media platforms with the purpose of marketing and promoting books (Chittal, 2018). The study of social media marketing has been concerned significantly by researchers and practitioners in today's technology era (Alalwan, 2018). This is because the researches that have been done on Social media marketing showed that SMM (Social media marketing) is the best opportunity to interact with existing and prospect customers and affect the purchase intention (Blakeman &

Brown, 2010). However, the challenge that companies face is that how to market the product or write content on social media in such a way that can attract the customers and influence their purchase intention based on (Alalwan, 2018). The research indicated that the community group that exist in social media is a great source to customer's knowledge that has an impact on customer purchase intention (Küster & Hernández, 2012).

Therefore, the research found that both traditional media and new social media affect the customer purchase intention, but the modern social media has more influence than the traditional media on customer purchase intention (Wright et al., 2016). Apart from that, one of the effective features of social media is E-WOM that has a great influence on customer intention, so the studies on social media marketing recommended to the marketer to ask customers to share their experience with the product and service instead of just posting advertisements and promotions (Kamaruddin, 2007). Furthermore, the study of Santoso and Cahyadi (2014) discovered that social media marketing is one of the significant factors that affect customer purchase intention. Therefore, due to the increasing number of social media users, and the importance of social media marketing, most of the companies, organizations, and retailers in different industries adopted social media marketing to affect or change customer purchase intention and it also can be effective in bookstores (Anas, Alhadid & Alhadeed, 2017).

H1: Social media marketing has a positive impact on customer purchase intention in the bookstores in Kurdistan.

Perceived usefulness and customer purchase intention

Perceived usefulness is one of the significant determinations of technology acceptance behaviour. So, Davis (1989) defined the perceived usefulness as "the degree to which a

person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance". In that study, the perceived usefulness had a direct impact on customer purchase intention toward accepting new technology. To put it more specifically, it is about how much social media is useful or effective for customers to search and buy products. Means that customers are able to get many benefits from shopping via social media such as convenient buying, getting more information to compare the products and having more power which can affect the customer's purchase intention (Perea et al., 2004).

Furthermore, Gefen (2000) stated that in most of the studies perceived ease to use has an impact on customer purchase intention but through perceived usefulness. In addition to that, technology acceptance behaviour is significantly influenced by Perceived usefulness and attitude (Lee & Cheung, 2005). Likewise, the other study showed the same result that the attitude and perceived usefulness have a great influence on customer purchase intention (Perea et al., 2004). Apart from that, the research of Ramus and Nielsen (2005) showed that perceived usefulness has a great impact on customer purchase intention toward buying food via online, this is because buying foods through online has more advantages such as more convenience, providing a wider variety of foods, and saving time (Chien & Kurnia, 2003). Moreover, in online shopping, the perceived usefulness has a considerable impact on customer purchase intention (Aldmour & Sarayrah, 2016). To put it more specific, perceived usefulness is one of the factors that affect customers purchase intention in those bookstores that have a virtual platform to market the books such as website, social media, and E-commerce (Nguyen et al., 2020).

H2: Perceived usefulness has a positive impact on customer purchase in the bookstores in Kurdistan.

Perceived ease of use and customer purchase intention

Perceived ease of use is one of the considerable determinations of technology acceptance behaviour, and Davis (1989) defined the perceived ease of use as "the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular system would be free of physical and mental effort". So, that study of Davis (1989) indicated that perceived ease of use had an indirect impact on customer purchase intention in accepting new technology. To put it in specific, it is about how much social media can make shopping easier for customers (Perea et al., 2004).

Furthermore, the research found that perceived ease of use has a positive influence on perceived usefulness, means that the easier the use of technology the more the technology would be useful for customers (Nguyen et al., 2019). Along with that according to the study of Athapaththu and Kulathunga (2018), the factor of perceived ease of use has a direct impact on customer purchase intention. Furthermore, the study Renny, Guritno and Siringoringo (2013) indicated that there is a positive relationship between perceived ease of use and customer purchase intention in online shopping. Specifically, perceived ease of use is one of the factors that affect customers purchase intention in those bookstores that own the virtual platform such as website, social media, and E-commerce (Nguyen et al., 2020).

H3: Perceived ease of use has a positive impact on customer purchase intention in the bookstores in Kurdistan.

Attitude and customer purchase intention

Attitude can be defined as a positive or negative feeling toward an object that will affect the individual's behaviour (Schiffman et al., 2005). Attitude consists of three elements which are conative, affective, and behaviour (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1977). Attitude can be considered as one of the most significant indicators of customer purchase intention based on (Alalwan, 2018). So, according to the theory of TPB, there are three

major factors to predict the customer intention and one of them is customer Attitude (Anep et al., 2007).

Furthermore, in online shopping, customer attitude refers to customer's tendency toward using the technology for shopping or how much the customer is ready or willing to do virtual shopping (Delafruz & Sidin., 2009). In addition to that, empirically, in the study of Orapin (2009). The planned behaviour module (TPB) was used to examine the Thai customer's intention toward shopping via online and three factors were chosen to determine the purchase intention, and one of them was customer attitude and the result of the study indicated that there is a positive relationship between attitude and Thai customer's purchase intention. Apart from that,

the research of Davis (1993) discovered that there is a direct, strong and positive relationship between attitude and customer intention toward accepting to utilize new technology. Likewise, according to the study of Eri, Islam and Daud (2011), the attitude has a significant impact on customer purchase intention toward technology acceptance and the internet specifically. Moreover, there is a positive relationship between a student's attitude and online shopping according to the study of Delafruz et al., (2009). The study found that most of the Malaysian students prefer to search and purchase books at the bookstore virtual platforms (Delafruz et al., 2009).

H4: Attitude has a positive impact on customer purchase intention in the bookstores in Kurdistan.

Conceptual framework

Figure 2. The proposed conceptual framework

Figure 2. indicated the proposed conceptual framework which is the impact of independent variables social media marketing, attitude, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use on dependent variable which is customer purchase intention.

METHOD, DATA, AND ANALYSIS

Therefore, the quantitative approach was followed in this study to test the hypothesis and the theory of Technology acceptance model. The researcher followed a quantitative approach because the large sample was selected to study on, and the researcher relied on the quantitate analysis to explain and understand the topic.

Another reason is that a quantitative method is considered as an efficient way to test the hypothesis (Birks, 2016).

Regarding data collection, the online self-administrated questionnaire was distributed via social media to those people who are interested in reading books in Kurdistan, by approaching those bookshops who are actively using social media to promote their books to the customers and ask them to post the survey to the followers of their social media pages/ sites. Therefore, the questionnaire was distributed or posted it in the book community groups on social media as well. In terms of sampling design, non-probability purposive sampling was used in this research. This is because a specific group of customers based on Particular criteria was selected based on researcher's purpose, and this method is widely used among the researcher for testing the hypothesis (Farrimond & Farrimond, 2013).

When it comes to sampling size, Solvin's formula was utilized in the present study to design the sample size of the population. According to (DATAREPORTAL, 2020) the number of people who are using social media is 21 million in 2020 in whole Iraq, and Kurdistan region is make-up of the 15% of Iraq's population (CNN, 2020) So, the number of people who are using social media in Kurdistan is estimated to be 1.4 million in 2020. Hence, the population size of the present study is 1.4 million. Statistics the N=1,400,000 and the

margin of error = 0.06. So, the sample size of the population for the present study is estimated to be:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1.400.000}{1 + 1.400.000 \times 0.06^2}$$

N=278

Therefore, the result that is given by the Slovin's formula is 278 sample size. Therefore, the researcher targeted at least 278 sample size to study the impact of social media marketing on customer purchase intention in the bookstore.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Exploratory factor analysis

EFA is used to summarize or transfer the data collections into a manageable form by investigating or exploring the interrelationship among all the variables to discover inappropriate items and removing them or adding other items instead, so that the data would be ready for further analysis which is multiple regression analysis (Zulkepli et al., 2017). So, in this study for the rotation method, the researcher used varimax rotation for the component extraction method for data reduction analysis (Che Rusuli et al., 2013). In the present study, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value was 0.879 for the factor analysis test as shown in table 4.4 , which indicates that the data were significant and suitable for the principal component analysis (Che Rusuli et al., 2013).

Table 2. KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.879
Bartlett's Approx. Chi-Square		2213.044
Test of df		153
Sphericity Sig.		.000

Once the confirmation of factor analysis proved, Principle Component Analysis (PCA) was conducted with Varimax by the researcher to

analyses the results. (Dean, 2009) recommended that values of factor loading can be considered useful if they are 0.4 and greater.

Table 3. Exploratory factor analysis

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Attitude3	.781			
Attitude4	.745			
Attitude2	.730			
Attitude1	.718			
Attitude5	.573			
SMM1		.703		
SMM2		.695		
SMM3		.680		
SMM4		.639		
SMM5		.621		
PU4			.713	
PU3			.712	
PU5			.629	
PU2			.619	
PU1			.561	
PEOU2				.769
PEOU3				.696
PEOU5				.562

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.

It can be observed from table 3. that two items have been removed which are PEOU1, and PEOU4. The omission of PEOU 1, PEOU 2 was because they load on another component (PU). So, eliminating cross-loadings assist to interpret

the factors, as when one item loads on one factor only the factor structure will be simple and clear. In another word If the items significantly load on multiple factors, the factors will not be interpreted easily (Che Rusuli et al., 2013).

Table 4. Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.690	37.168	37.168	6.690	37.168	37.168	3.168	17.600	17.600
2	1.836	10.198	47.366	1.836	10.198	47.366	2.938	16.323	33.923
3	1.160	6.443	53.809	1.160	6.443	53.809	2.644	14.690	48.613
4	1.060	5.890	59.700	1.060	5.890	59.700	1.996	11.087	59.700

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

In this study analysis, the researcher needs to produce four factors with 18 items, whereby, Attitude presented by (5 items with 37%),

followed by SMM presented by (items with 10%) then PU presented by (5 items with 6%), and minimally PEOU presented by (3 items with 5.8 %) as shown in table 4.3. it is also shown in table

4. that, four variances showed high Eigenvalues using the Varimax rotation method among eighteen other components, the highest component value presented by (1.060 or 60%) from the cumulative value. While, as the lowest component was presented by (6.690 or 37%) from the cumulative value.

The multiple regression analysis is defined by (Simon, 2003) as a method to test the level or the strength of relationships between several independent variables and a dependent variable. So, it can be seen in table 5. that the result of R square was .462, which means that approximately 46% of the variation in the dependent variable is accounted by the independent variables.

Multiple regression analysis

Table 5. The multi regression analysis summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.685 ^a	.469	.462	.68958

Table 6. Regression analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.453	.182		2.489	.013
SMM	.186	.062	.169	3.003	.003
PU	.029	.014	.116	2.047	.042
PEOU	.257	.046	.289	5.546	.000
Attitude	.273	.048	.297	5.744	.000

Table 7. ANOVA multiple regression

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	123.888	4	30.972	65.134	.000 ^b
	Residual	140.277	295	.476		
	Total	264.166	299			

In this study, as shown in table 7. ANOVA multiple linear regression was utilized to examine variance in customer purchase intention toward bookstores for 300 respondents, using the Enter method. A significant model (F-value = 65.134, P-value = 0.00) predicted about 124% of the sample outcome variance (Adjusted R2 =

0.462) which means that independent variables explained 46.2% to the dependent variable. Four predictors were entered into the model and all were significantly associated with customer purchase intention toward bookstores. SMM (beta = .169, t-value = 3.003, P-value = <0.01). As well as Attitude (beta = .297, t-value = 5.744, P-

value = <0.01) followed by PEOU (β .289=, t-value =5.546, P-value = <0.01) and finally PU (β =.116, t-value =2.047, P-value = <0.04). In summary, since the coefficients of the all the four independent variables were all in the

direction hypothesized with statistical significance level at ($p < 0.05$), so the result would be that all the four predictor variables are supported as shown in table 8.

Table 8. Hypothesis testing decision

No.	Hypothesized paths	Decision
H1	Perceived usefulness has a positive impact on customer purchase in the bookstores in Kurdistan.	Supported
H2	Perceived ease of use has a positive impact on customer purchase intention in the bookstores in Kurdistan.	Supported
H3	Attitude has a positive impact on customer purchase intention in the bookstores in Kurdistan.	Supported
H4	Social media marketing has a positive impact on customer purchase intention in the bookstores in Kurdistan.	Supported

DISCUSSION

Does perceived usefulness has an impact on customer purchase intention in the bookstores in Kurdistan?

Based on the results of this study, perceived usefulness does have a significant positive impact on consumer purchase intention as the path coefficient analysis shows that there is a strong relationship between perceived usefulness and customer purchase intention with ($\beta = 0.116$). So, the result shows that perceived usefulness significantly influence customers who buy books at social media pages of bookstores. Regarding previous studies, according to (Ganguly et al., 2010) in most of the E-commerce businesses Perceived usefulness has a direct effect on customer purchase intention and also the research of (Jen et al., 2009) reported the same result. Moreover, in online shopping, the perceived usefulness has a considerable impact on customer purchase intention (Aldhmour & Sarayrah, 2016). To put it more specific, perceived usefulness is one of the factors that

affect customers purchase intention in those bookstores that have a virtual platform to market the books such as website, social media, and E-commerce (Nguyen et al., 2020).

Does perceive ease of use has an impact on customer purchase intention in the bookstores in Kurdistan?

Based on the results of this study, perceived ease of use does have a significant positive impact on consumer purchase intention as the path coefficient analysis shows that there is a strong relationship between PEOU and purchase intention with ($\beta = .289$). Which means the result of this study shows that perceived ease of use significantly impacts on customers that buy books at social media pages of bookstores.

There are many studies that supported that perceived ease of use has a significant impact on customer purchase intention toward virtual platforms. The study of Yuuhaa et al. (2018) analyzed three factors that affect Malaysian

young customer purchase intention toward online shopping and the result showed that those three factors had a significant impact and one of the major factors was perceived ease of use. Furthermore, the study (Renny et al., 2013) indicated that there is a positive relationship between perceived ease of use and customer purchase intention in online shopping. Specifically, perceived ease of use is one of the factors that affect customers purchase intention in those bookstores that own the virtual platform such as website, social media, and E-commerce (Nguyen et al., 2020).

Does customer attitude has an impact on customer purchase intention in the bookstores in Kurdistan?

According to the results of this research, attitude does have a significant positive impact on consumer purchase intention as the path coefficient analysis shows that there is a strong relationship between attitude and customer purchase intention with ($\beta = 0.297$). These results also show that consumers who show a positive attitude toward social media pages of bookstores they are most likely purchasing books. Numerous studies showed that there is a positive relationship between attitude and customer purchase intention toward shopping via virtual platforms. In the study of Orapin (2009) there were certain factors used to examine the Thai customer's intention toward shopping via online and three factors were chosen to determinate the purchase intention, and one of them was customer attitude and the result of the study indicated that there is a positive relationship between attitude and Thai customer's purchase intention. Apart from that, the research of Davis (1993) discovered that there is a direct, strong and positive relationship between attitude and customer intention toward accepting to utilize new technology. Likewise, according to the study of Eri et al. (2011), the attitude has a significant impact on customer purchase intention toward technology acceptance and the internet specifically. Moreover, according to the study of

Delafrooz et al. (2009), there is a positive relationship between a student's attitude and online shopping. The study of Delafrooz et al., (2009) found that most of the Malaysian students prefer to search and purchase books at the bookstore virtual platforms.

Does social media marketing has an impact on customer purchase intention in the bookstores in Kurdistan? SMM with

The findings of the study showed that there is a significant positive relationship between social media marketing and customer purchase intention toward purchasing books as the path coefficient analysis shows that there is a strong relationship between social media marketing and customer purchase intention with ($\beta = .169$). Which indicates that doing social media marketing by bookstores significantly influence customers to buy books.

Regarding the previous studies, the study of Santoso and Cahyadi (2014) supported that social media marketing is one of the significant factors that affect customer purchase intention. The study reported that great awareness is essential to make the customer think about the brand whenever he or she wants to buy products, and social media is a significant platform to create awareness for the brand and charge the customer's intention (Keller, 2009). Besides, the research found that both traditional media and new social media affect customer purchase intention, but modern social media is more than the traditional one (Wright et al., 2016). Therefore, the finding of this study has made a great contribution to the body of literature that there is a strong relationship between social media marketing and customer purchase intention.

THE IMPLICATION OF THE STUDY

Since there is no online bookstore or E-commerce business for the customers to buy books online in Kurdistan (Jaffar, 2016). On the other hand, many customers complain about the

problem of the parking facility, most of the bookstore locations have no enough parking space nearby for the customers to be able to visit the bookstores and spend quite enough time to search for books and buying them. So, due to that, the researchers have decided to study the impact of social media pages of a bookstore on customer purchase intention. Interestingly, the finding of this study showed that social media marketing has a significant impact on customer purchase intention toward bookstores in the region, which means that customers tend to purchase books through social media pages of bookstores. Furthermore, having social media pages is crucial for the bookstores in the region to facilitate customers to purchase books. So, bookstore marketers need to include social media marketing to their promotional strategy and improving social media marketing skills can be a competitive advantage for the bookstores. Apart from that, the finding of the study indicated that the easiness of use and the usefulness of the social media pages of bookstores play a very important role to influence the customer purchase intention. So, the bookstore marketers should highlight the usefulness and ease of use of social media pages of bookstores to their customers, to increase the usage of social media pages of bookstores and influence their purchase intention. In addition to that, the more the customer has a positive attitude toward social media pages of bookstores, the more it influences their purchase intention. So, the bookstore marketers may able to form a positive customer's attitude toward social media pages of bookstores.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

The limitation of the previous study made this research significant. Meanwhile, the contribution of this study is going to be a limitation of future studies to fill the gap. The study limitation will be categorized in the following areas: First, the researcher only targets four provinces of the Kurdistan region of Iraq, so the result of this study would not represent the whole provinces of Iraq. Second, the result showed that there is a significant relationship

between social media marketing and customer purchase intention. However, the result might be different if the study were conducting in a developed country that enjoys online bookstore or E-commerce. Therefore, this study cannot be generalized to all the bookstores worldwide. Third, this study examined the impact of social media marketing in bookstore retailers specifically. Means that the findings of this research cannot be generalized to other types of retailers.

It can be recommended to potential researchers to further study on the bookstore retailers, due to the lack of research and studies in this area. Also, it can be recommended to future researchers to study other factors that might have an impact on customer purchase intention toward bookstores such as in-store marketing. Meanwhile, potential researchers can expand the population target to the whole provinces of Iraq.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of social media marketing on consumer purchase intention toward bookstores in Kurdistan. The study sample consisted of people who live in four provinces in the Kurdistan region of Iraq (Erbil, Sulaymaniyah, Duhok, Halabja). The study conceptual framework adapted the TPB and TAM theoretical framework. In this study, the researcher examined the impact of Attitude, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, as independents variables of the TPB & TAM model, and SMM as the study main objective.

The result of the study indicated that all the TAM variables have a significant impact on the consumer purchase intention toward bookstores. SMM also showed a significant positive impact on consumer purchase intention.

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